

Tips for anonymising and pseudonymising

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This document provides tips and actions you can take when you want to anonymise or pseudonymise your research data.

General tips and actions

Look at the bigger picture

Combining data with other information in your dataset, your research or even elsewhere in the world may lead to identification. A rule of thumb at Radboud University is that a group can be considered anonymous when there are at least ten individuals in that group.

Examples:

1. Combining variables within your dataset might lead to identification. A class might have ten students from Asia, which can be considered anonymous by the rule of thumb mentioned above. However, if you also know that this group of ten students consists of five male, three female and two non-binary individuals, these subgroups are no longer anonymous.
2. The combination of age specified in days and test date leads to the date of birth. In this case, either the test date can be reduced to the year, or the unit of age can be adjusted to month or year.
3. Datasets that include exact occupations may result in identification of the respondents. 'Nurse' or 'teacher' may not be very revealing, but 'director of [company X]' or 'leader of [religious community Y]' are, since a quick internet search may reveal the individual. Exact occupations may be adjusted to occupational groups using the [ISCO method](#).
4. An outlier might become an identifier if you know the context. The context might not be known to everybody, but the participants can often identify fellow participants if they are from the same research pool (e.g. company, school, community, etc), making your data no longer anonymous. For example:
 - a. One extremely tall or small person in a company can be identified by colleagues and by anyone who knows that company.
 - b. The only student with nationality X in a classroom can be easily identified if you know the school(s) in which the research was done. This *might* be solved by aggregating at the level of continent.
 - c. Grouped variables (e.g. brackets of age or work experience) can still contain identifiable information when the research pool is known. It might be that the lowest or highest bracket contain less than ten individuals and thus violating the above mentioned rule of thumb.

Textual information

Answers to open ended questions might contain personal information and/or information that you did not ask for since participants can often type or say anything they want. First of all, try to avoid open ended questions if you suspect that your participants might enter personal information. If the questionnaire has not been distributed yet, reformulate the question so that you minimize the chances of collecting accidental personal information. For already collected questions, check all answers and remove any personal information.

Other textual information, such as notes, documentation, code or annotations might also contain personal data. *Examples:* “Ask John D. for opinion on this topic” or “Code written by Bob D.”. Check these type of files and remove all personal information from them.

Other versions of your data

Be aware that if you have another version of your data that includes personal data stored separate, your data is considered pseudonymised and not anonymised! This includes all versions on your own work-in-progress storage, in download folders and even email conversations with participants.

Example: You archived your raw research data including personal data, then published a processed version of your data from which you removed all identifying information. Since the archived dataset can be linked to your published dataset, the published dataset is considered to be pseudonymous, not anonymous. Therefore, the GDPR still applies!

Audio and video data

Transcribing audio and video data

Audio and video data are, by definition, personal data: people can be identified by their physical appearance, their behaviour and/or voice. Transcribing audio and video data can help significantly when you want to pseudonymise or anonymise your data.

De-identify transcripts: remove personal data or replace it with a placeholder in the transcript. For example: “Elementary, my dear [name colleague].” or “[name dog], I've a feeling we're not in [place of residence] anymore.”

After transcription, some research institutes at Radboud University recommend that you remove the original recordings. Deleting the original personal data could help you anonymise instead of pseudonymise. Check the [RDM policy of your institute](#) to see what is suggested.

Alternatively, you can also blur or transform a recording.

Scans

Defacing scans

Brain images that include facial regions can be used to identify the research subjects. Blurring or removing these facial features are highly recommended. For more details on defacing scans while maintaining scientific value to your dataset, see the article of Eke et al. (2021; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ynirp.2021.100053>).

'Hidden' metadata

Some file formats contain personal data in their metadata that you might not always be aware of. For example, DICOM files may contain patient names, patient numbers or date of birth. In those cases, remove the metadata from the DICOM files.